

GREEN PURCHASING INTENTION AMONG JORDANIAN CUSTOMERS

JASSIM AHMAD AL-GASAWNEH¹ and MARHANA MOHAMED ANUAR²

¹Marketing Department, Business Faculty, Applied Science Private University, Amman – Jordan.
Email: j_algasawneh@asu.edu.jo

²Department of Marketing, Faculty of Business, Economics and Social Development, Universiti of Malaysia Terengganu, Terengganu, Malaysia. Email: marhana@umt.edu.my

Abstract

This quantitative study explored the effect of content marketing and green purchasing intention Jordan. The data for this study was derived from a survey questionnaire completed by the customers. a total of 230 questionnaires were involved to the data analysis. The results were analyzed by using partial least squares structural equation modelling. The outcome of the analysis showed that the effect content marketing and green purchasing intention. Hence, this study provides practical evidence to assist the companies in the Jordan to attain the customer intention to purchase the green products through display effective marketing contents.

INTRODUCTION

With the energy crisis and increasingly serious environmental problems, green consumption has been given more and more attention from companies and consumers. Consumers are striving to search and purchase green products that are environmentally friendly due to environmental considerations (Chen et al., 2015; Goh and Balaji, 2016). Thus, in the journey of search consumers will seek information and check reviews of the product before purchasing. Other than depending on the advertising messages by companies (Shukor, 2015), In the Internet era, the methods and media of content marketing are more diversified. Online content marketing is always educational and they are constantly presented on the Internet in an interesting way, lowering the requirement for the cognitive ability of the audience. Dispersed as Barber et. al. (2010) suggests that researchers should investigate consumers' purchase intentions for green products. Jordan's lack of environmental concern and sustainability management is clearly evident. According to Arab Forum for Environment and Development (2017), the majority (53%) of the respondents in Jordan believes that the environmental situation in Jordan is getting worse compared to the last ten years. Jordan confronts a variety of challenges in sustainable development and remains in the early stages of green initiation (Alsmadi, 2007; Zu'bi et al., 2015). The current study investigates the influence of content marketing on increasing the green purchase intention.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Content marketing

Content marketing also is known as Advertorials (Vinerean, 2017), as an advertisement, are articles in a newspaper, magazine, or a website which involves giving information about the

product. Usually, brands pay publishers for such articles. Marketers use them to educate potential consumers about the characteristics of content marketing of the product. By choosing the right media, content marketing can be used for a specific group of people. For example, content marketing in business newspapers would involve educating a group of people who are more interested in economics, markets or financial products. For companies, storytelling is an effective medium to connect with consumers, which is unlike traditional print advertising in magazines, newspapers or on websites as a banner advertising. Content marketing is more detailed than advertising, which helps consumers to know more about products and is usually written by advertising agents or companies themselves. In the Internet era, the methods and media of content marketing are more diversified. Online content marketing is always educational and they are constantly presented on the Internet in an interesting way, lowering the requirement for the cognitive ability of the audience. Therefore, online content marketing is often more effective than traditional advertisements (Bunpis&Haron 2014; Xiao& Liu, 2019).

Milhinhos, (2015) indicated that the concealment of content marketing (which is often criticized) and the independence of the news media have made people unwittingly pleasing and thus won over their trust. Some of the content marketing, such as those created by prominent bloggers and Internet celebrities, have even enhanced the perceived value of their fans to the products. Wang, & Yang (2014) believe that customers can obtain useful information about the goods from the content marketing posted on the e-commerce platform in a short span of time so that they do not have to make great efforts for shopping. This study relied on Xiao et al (2019) to measure the content marketing perception through making the customer familiar with goods, present the product benefits and attract the customer attention and impress the customers, at last, to create effective marketing content.

GREEN PURCHASING INTENTION

Green products are known to have a less environmental impact or are less detrimental to human health than traditional products. “Green” can be defined as being ‘low polluting, recyclable and resource-saving’⁴. In general, green products are known as ecological products or environmentally friendly products. In other words, green products refer to a product that incorporates strategies in recycling or are made with recycled content, reduced packaging or uses fewer toxic materials in production or packaging to reduce the impact on the natural environment¹⁴. These green products are meant to be environmentally safe. Some examples of green products include green cars such as hybrid cars, recycled products, energy-efficient electronics, organic tea, body care products, among others. Purchase intention refers to how a consumer prefers to buy a product or service because he or she finds that a particular product or service fits their needs and attitudes towards a product and perception of the product¹⁵. Green purchase intention is conceptualized as the probability and willingness of a person to give preference to products having eco-friendly features over other traditional products under their purchase considerations (Rahim et al, 2016). Green purchase intention is an essential factor of the actual green buying behavior of a consumer. It means the customer intends to buy the green product if happened acts attract him or her to that.

METHODOLOGY

The current research is descriptive in its nature. Descriptive research can be defined as describe something some phenomena or any specific condition. Descriptive researches are those represents that represents the existing situation and making a decision. The key idea of descriptive research is to verify the developed hypothesis that reflects the existing situation. In order to gather the data for understanding the condition of green marketing, it was decided that the sample could be formed by individuals who are customers over the age of 22 –years old. The reason is Individuals above this age are well known concerning the purchasing of products and are also empowered in their decisions for selecting the right items between many available choices. A self-administered online questionnaire was distributed in Amman capital of Jordan through social media sits, emails because Amman is a capital of Jordan crowded by citizen and factories than other cities. The questionnaire consisted of 15 questions in total and was divided into three parts. In part 1, the items about the independent variable (content marketing) were placed. In part 2, the dependent variable (green purchase intention) was presented and in part 3, respondents were asked about their socio-demographic characteristics. The questionnaire items used five Likert scales. Tow step conducted to ensure from the questioner validation and reliability which the first step was by sending the questionnaire to the academic experts who are professors in universities and we modified all them comments, the second step was test the internal consistency through extracted the Cronbach alpha for the variables were (content marketing 0.83; and the green purchase intention 0, 73) from the two steps that conducted the instrument was valid and reliable. Sample size should be based on the power of analysis, which is the minimum number of samples based on the model complexity. Based on Green’s (1991) table, with 2 predictors from the research framework, at medium effect size as suggested by Gefen et al. (2011), the minimum sample size is 74. In line with (hair, 2010) to get the accurate result the sample need to be more than 100. For that, the current study distributed 300 questionnaires to the customers. Table 1 represents the study variables, item numbers and sources of adapted scales. PLS-SEM software used in the research data analysis.

Table 1: Scales Used in Research

No	Variable	No of items	Reference
1	content marketing (CM)	5	Xiao et al (2019)
3	green purchase intention (GPI)	5	Rahim et al (2016)

RESULT

215 questionnaires were returned, 13 questionnaires excluded because of the incompleteness, the total amount of usable questionnaires in this study was 202, mal female.....

CFA Model for Research Model

A total of 13 items were employed in the measurement of 3 first-order constructs in (CM, E-WOM, and GPI). They are as follows: CM included 5 items, and GPI included 5 items. In the evaluation of the measurement model of the research model, the study employed the confirmatory factor analysis. Figure 4.1 highlights the measurement model

Convergent Validity

The confirmatory factor analysis for the measurements models as showed in Table 2

Table 2: The Result of Cronbach’s Alpha and Convergent Validity for the CFA Model on the Research Model

Construct	Items	Factor loading	CR	AVE
CM	CM 1	0.854	0.928	0.721
	CM 2	0.77		
	CM 3	0.828		
	CM 4	0.925		
	CM5	0.860		
GPI	GPI 1	0.877	0.891	0.622
	GPI 2	0.839		
	GPI 3	0.778		
	GPI 4	0.767		
	GPI 5	0.666		

Table 2 displays the evaluation outcomes of the standardized factor loadings of model items. As can be observed, the standardized factor loadings were all greater than 0.6 (the loadings range from 0.666 to 0.925). As can be seen also, the values of AVE for all constructs ranged from 0.622 to 0.740. These values were all greater the cut-off value of 0.5 as proposed by Hair et al. (2010). Furthermore, the values of composite reliability for all constructs were ranged from 0.891 to 0.934, and these obtained values all surpassed the proposed value of 0.7 for all constructs as in (Hair et al, 2010).

Discriminant validity

The current study obtained HTMT to measure the Discriminant validity for the model following to (Henseler, 2015).

Table 3: The HTMT for constructs

	CM	GPI
CM		
GPI	0.733	

As shows in table 3, all the HTMT values of the constructs were below 0.90, ranged from 0.641 to 0.739. Therefore, it confirms that each latent construct measurement was totally discriminating to each other (Henseler et al., 2015). Upon examining convergent validity and discriminant validity of the measurement model, it can be concluded that the measurement scale to assess the constructs and their relative items in CFA model was reliable and valid.

Hypothesized Direct Effects of the Constructs in Structural Model

The hypothesis test and relationship in this section as shown in table 4.

Table 4: Hypothesized Direct Effects Structural Model

Path	St. β	St. d	R ²	Q ²	F ²	VIF	T-value	P-value
CM > GPI	0.416	0.155	0.551	0.301	0.239	1.612	2.690	0.007

As can be observed in Table 4.5 The value of R² for GPI, was 0.551,. This indicates, for example, 55.1 percent of variations in GPI is explained by its predictors (CM) the value satisfy the requirement for the 0.19 cut off value as recommended by (Chin, 1998). The values of Q² for GPI was 0.301 far greater than zero which refers to predictive relevance of the model as suggested by (Chin, 2010), the model exhibits an acceptable fit and high predictive relevance. While the VIF value was 1.612 which was less than 5, (Hair, 2014). Further in the prediction GPI, the p-value of CM, was 0.007. This means that the probabilities of achieving through absolute p-value are 0.01 and 0.05. Further, the path coefficient (S, B) values for (CM to GPI), was 0.416 and this denotes relationships that are positive, thus all of above discussion leading to support H.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In previous works on content marketing and purchasing intention in investigating the influence of content marketing on consumer purchase intention this study through result of H1 agreed with (Yaqubi & Karaduman, 2019) result that effective and suitable content marketing leading to attract the consumers toward the green purchasing intention , meanwhile in line with Ramzan & Syed (2018) about role of content-based social media marketing in motivating consumers to forwarding content through spread e- word of mouth, This study contributes through applying the social communication (SC) Theory to cover the examination the relationship between content marketing and green purchasing intention. Further analyzed the data by used PLS 3 software.

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E-Word of mouth questionnaire (Source: Al-Debei, 2015); Septiari, E. D. (2018).

I often read online recommendations to buy products.

2. I often post positive online comments about the products.
3. I often read positive online reviews about the products
4. My e-community frequently post online recommendations regarding the products.
5. Consumer's online recommendations and reviews make me more confident to purchase the product

Content marketing items (Xiao et al, 2019)

1. Content marketing on makes me feel more familiar with goods
2. Content marketing is useful to me
3. I will pay special attention to content marketing
4. Content marketing can impress me toward the products
5. I will trust the content marketing

Green intention (Rahim et al, 2016)

1. I intend to buy green products because they are less polluting to the environment.
2. I intend to switch to green products for ecological reasons.
3. When I want to buy a product, I look at the ingredient label to see if it contains things that are environmentally damaging.
4. I prefer green products over non - green products when their product qualities are similar.
5. I buy green products even if they are more expensive than the non - green ones.